

Polypropylene micro-and nanoplastics affects the digestion of cow's milk proteins in infants

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Infants are exposed to and ingest more micro-and nanoplastics (MNPs) than any other age group¹; however, the effect of MNPs on the digestion of proteins in infants is not known. Therefore, the current study investigated the *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk proteins in the presence of polypropylene MNPs (PP-MNPs) in simulated gastric fluids (SGF) using infant digestion model (pH=5.0; pepsin activity=268 U/mL). The simulated *in vitro* digestion of skimmed (<1% fat) cow's milk proteins in infants in the presence of PP-MPs (20 mg/mL; 63–180 µm in size) was done at 37 °C for 5, 30, and 120 min. The *in vitro* digestion experiment was repeated with different concentrations of PP-NPs (125, 250, and 500 µg/mL) for 30 min. Another experiment was set up using adult gastrointestinal conditions (pH=3.0; pepsin activity=2000 U/mL) for comparison purposes². The final concentration of the cow's milk protein in the digestion mixture was 1 mg/mL. Then, proteins binding to the PP-MNPs were extracted from the soft corona and hard corona using the centrifugation method and protein profiles were analyzed using SDS-PAGE. The bands of proteins of interest were carefully excised from the gels and analysed by LC-MS/MS. Both PP-MPs and PP-NPs negatively affected the digestion of proteins in infants, and binding was observed in both the soft and hard corona. Meanwhile, no significant effects of both PP-MPs and PP-NPs on protein digestion were observed in adults. These results suggest possible interference of MNPs with the utilization of proteins in infants, which could have detrimental health effects.

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